

SYNONYMOUS RANGE AND EUPHEMICAL CLASSIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the opinions expressed about synonyms in the Uzbek language. In the main analysis, the use of graduonymic relations in speech is discussed among euphemistic synonymous lexemes.

It is known that sufficient scientific research works on synonymy have been carried out both in world linguistics and in Uzbek linguistics. In Uzbek linguistics, the phenomenon of synonymy has been deeply studied on the example of lexical, morphological, syntactic level units [1]. In these works, issues such as the essence of the phenomenon of synonymy, its formation factors, functional-stylistic features, its application at different levels, and its relationship with other related phenomena are analyzed.

Despite the large number of works devoted to the study of synonyms, the variety of definitions given to this phenomenon is noticeable in them. If we pay attention to the definitions given to synonyms in Uzbek linguistics, their definition is based first on the semantic similarity of the lexemes [2], then on the commonality of their meanings [3], and then on the semantic similarity (exactly) It is observed that it is based on [4]. We can see that in most of the initial definitions, ideas were led for a long time based on the exact sameness of the meanings expressed by synonymous lexemes.

In the subsequent studies devoted to the study of the phenomenon of synonymy, the definition of "same meaning" was abandoned, and attention was paid to aspects such as the semantic differences observed in synonymy, the sign of stylistic specificity, and the expression of connotation. Therefore, the emergence of synonymy is a leading concept in the linguistic features of euphemisms.

One of the lexical-semantic groups of lexemes in Uzbek linguistics, graduanim (gradation) was not monographically studied until the last decades of the last century, most of them were studied within the scope of synonymy.

Graduonymy (Gr. gradatio - "rise", "growth", *onymo* - "name") is the formation of a certain gradation series according to the mutual semantic relationship of lexical units. , was first promoted in Uzbek linguistics in the works of H. Nematov, S. Giyosov, R. Safarova. Monographic

research of this phenomenon in linguistics is related to candidate and doctoral studies of Sh. Orifjonova and O. Bozorov. In these studies, the place of graduonym as an independent lexical paradigm, its specific features [5], as well as the place of graduonym in the construction of the Uzbek language, the criteria and signs of gradual classification were determined [6]. After this process, we can also note that the terms graduonymy, graduonymic relation, gradation are used exactly as synonyms [7].

Synonymous relationship is the naming, naming and describing feature of the language, while graduonymic relationship represents the process of transition from quantitative changes in reality to qualitative changes, and in the euphemistic gradation series, as above, in the mild expression of reality, the growth and development of high culture in the meaning of lexemes we can observe that it is getting narrower.

In B. Mengliyev's textbook "Current Uzbek language" intended for students of higher philological education, synonyms and the relationship between them are described as "The forms are different, but the lexemes that express the same concept with different colors and shades are synonyms. The relationship between synonymous lexemes is called synonymy or synonymous relationship. The scientific paradigm of semantics is always open, some of them go out of use based on the demand of the society and the times, and the synonymous series are enriched with new ones. It emphasizes that the combination, the expansion of speech morpheme, these are considered as contextual synonyms as a tool that provides the beauty and richness of speech, synonymy is a linguistic phenomenon, and the synonymous series is not considered a lexical paradigm [8]. Also, B. Doniyorov, who conducted a research on synonyms, based on the results of his research, "Uzbek lexical synonyms are suitable for the main denotative meaning, but the characteristics and application (functional possibilities) of the connotative meaning components are measured." It is appropriate to describe them as synonyms that differ by their specificity [9]. Euphemistic synonyms also have graduonymic (leveling) relationships, as differentiation occurs in synonymous lines. We will analyze this below on the example of the KASAL (ILL) lexeme. We will try to analyze some differences in the grading of euphemisms: the factors of increasing the meaning, increasing the sign.

In the "Annotated dictionary of synonyms of the Uzbek language" synonyms of the lexeme KASAL are given as BETOB, NOTOB, BEMOR, NOSOG', XASTA, OG'RIQ. The normal functioning of the body is disturbed, it is the opposite of health. **Kasal** has a broad understanding. It is used only for a **Betob, notob, bemor, xasta** person. The words **Betob, notob** mean "temporarily ill". **Notob** is rarely used. A positive attitude is expressed in the word **Bemor** [3]. In a certain sense, there is a graduonymic relation of lexemes in this synonymous line, but the dictionary does not express any opinion about this.

The "short euphemistic dictionary of the Uzbek language" contains the following series of euphemistic lexemes. In this dictionary, lexemes are listed in alphabetical order. We tried to place it in a certain synonymous line based on the euphemistic graduonymic relationship. That is, **shamollamoq** → **tobi yo'q** → **tobi qochmoq** → **dardli** → **betob** → **bemor** → **xasta** etc. [10]. Here, all these and other lexical tools given as synonyms of this **kasal** lexeme are lexemes with euphemistic meaning used in its place. Although this dictionary is not given on the basis of graduonymic relationship between synonyms. We must understand this correctly, since the

work is compiled according to the traditions of dictionary compilation (in alphabetical order). This makes it necessary to create a "Euphemistic Grading Vocabulary" in the future, and it can be said that there is a need for it from the point of view of improving the current mother tongue education system. In the future, this will lead to positive results in the formation of the speech of the young generation at a high level, in the improvement of their concepts of manners and culture. For example, in this line, from the first (relatively mild) signs of the disease to the strongest sign, the meaning of the expression of softness, cultural, artistic, and euphemistic usage is increasing.

The view that the lexical semantic range is mainly a speech phenomenon, and synonymy is a linguistic phenomenon, has clarified a number of conflicting opinions on the separation of synonyms. The lexemes in semantic lines have the same meaning, and the expressions are semantically different, distinct and unique in each lexeme to a certain extent. As we have seen, there are meaningful differences in each series of lexemes from the above cold (a mild form of the disease sign) to the level of getting sick (a very severe disease sign), which is used in place of the word sick. In the euphemistic use of these lexemes, the lexemes of *shamollamoq* → *tobi yo'q* → *tobi qochmoq* → *dardli* → *betob* lexemes indicate that a person who is sick is still sick at home and the symptoms of the disease are gradually increasing, as well as *bemor* → *xasta* (the disease is very severe ir, in relation to a person admitted to the hospital) we observe.

Linguist M. Hakimova considers the phenomenon of graduonymy as a type of synonymy and evaluates such semantic relations as meaningful graduonymy [10]. In addition to this idea, it should also be said that euphemistic graduonymy is also a form of synonymy that is used instead of lexemes that acquire rough usage (increasing towards artistic, to the level of usage with high culture increase according to) is graded from the point of view. Some events and processes acquire a hierarchical (hierarchical) attitude in cultural expression and naming.

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